

Apolipoprotein L4 (APOL4) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : APOL is a class of classes of apolipoproteins, found in HDL complexes that play a central role in cholesterol transport. In the adult brain and during neurodevelopment, the modulation of gene transcription and signal transduction is governed by the cholesterol content of membranes. APOL-4 has been found to be highly up-regulated in schizophrenia. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of APOL4, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: APOL4, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

^{*}ML dicoveries of APOL4 synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossil, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinghieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Apolipoprotein

Apolipoproteins are proteins that bind lipids to form lipoproteins. They transport lipids in blood, cerebrospinal fluid and lymph. Lipids are a group of organic compounds which include fats, sterols, waxes, fat-soluble vitamins, mono/di-glycerides, phospholipids etc. A lipoprotein is a biochemical assembly that transports hydrophobic lipid molecules in water, blood plasma or other extracellular fluids. They consist of a triglyceride and cholesterol center, surrounded by a phospholipid outer shell, with the hydrophilic portions oriented outward toward the surrounding water and lipophilic portions oriented inward toward the lipid center. Plasma lipoprotein particles are classified into five main classes, based on size, lipid composition, and apolipoprotein content and in increasing size order, fall into : High-density lipoprotein (HDL), Low-density lipoprotein (LDL), Intermediate-density lipoprotein (IDL), Very-low-density lipopro-

tein (VLDL) and ultra low-density lipoproteins (ULDL or chylomicrons).

Even though the lipid components of lipoproteins are insoluble in water, because of their detergent-like (amphipathic i.e possessing both hydrophilic (water-loving, polar) and lipophilic (fat-loving, nonpolar)) properties, apolipoproteins and other amphipathic molecules can surround the lipids, creating a lipoprotein particle that is itself water-soluble, and can thus be carried through body fluids.

1.3. apolipoprotein L4 (APOL4)

Now, there are several classes of apolipoproteins of which Apolipoprotein L (Apo L) is one of them. APOL is found in HDL complexes that play a central role in cholesterol transport. In the adult brain and during neurodevelopment, the modulation of gene transcription and signal transduction is governed by the cholesterol content of membranes.

Previously, Duchateau et al. [13] identified and cloned the cDNA for a new protein, APOL, present in plasma, which associated with large high density lipoprotein particles. Duchateau et al. [13] characterized the gene for APOL and for three additional, highly homologous proteins that constituted a new family that showed no homology with previously described apolipoproteins. They observed that the genes for all four proteins, APOL-1/2/3/4 were located at chromosome 22q12.1-13.1 within a 127,000-bp region. Further, they found that all four genes had TATA-less promoters (containing sterol regulatory elements), thus suggesting that transcription of these genes might be coordinated with LDL receptor and genes in pathways involving the synthesis of triglycerides and cholesterol. APOL-1/2/3 were found to be expressed to the highest degree in the lung. Other tissues with high expression that were observed were the pancreas, prostate, spleen, liver, and placenta.

Page et al. [14] reported the cloning of a new gene family encoding six APOL-1/2/3/4/5/6 proteins. They found each APOL to share significant identity in its predicted amphipathic alpha helices while phylogenetic tree mapping showed the genes to be evolutionarily conserved. Further tissue distribution revealed expression in all tissues, but consistently higher levels in the placenta were observed, except for APOL-5. Their comparison of tissue distribution with APOA-1 (major structural component of HDL), suggested that the APOL proteins might play a role in lipid biochemistry. Lastly, they observed that the pathological expression of the APOLs during pregnancy was implicated in preeclampsia, fetal growth retardation, and the onset of adult atherosclerosis.

Mimmack et al. [15] screened a custom-made candidate gene cDNA array comprising 300 genes which were either implicated in schizophrenia or were located on high-susceptibility chromosome locations. Their array screening using prefrontal cortex tissue from 10 schizophrenia and 10 control brains showed up-regulation of APOL1 by 2.6-fold. Their findings were cross-validated using prefrontal cortex tissue from the Stanley Foundation brain collection, Bethesda, MD which consists of 15 schizophrenia, 15 bipolar disorder, 15 major depression, and 15 control individuals, with antipsychotic drug exposure in the schizophrenia and bipolar disorder groups. Further, they confirmed the up-regulation of APOL1 gene expression in schizophrenia and using quantitative PCR, found that APOL-2/4 were highly up-regulated in schizophrenia.

They further confirmed their results on independent set of 20 each of schizophrenia and control brains, from Japan and New Zealand. They report that all six APOL genes were located on chromosome 22q12, which was a confirmed high-susceptibility locus for schizophrenia and close to the region associated with velocardiofacial syndrome that includes symptoms of schizophrenia.

Monajemi et al. [16] showed that the APOL-1/2/3/4APOL4 cluster might contribute to the differences in the lipid metabolism of mice and humans.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [17] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [18] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [18].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [19]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [20], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [17] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [17]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [21], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the non-linearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. APOL4 related synergies

Note - APOL4 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of APOL4 were recorded.

3.1.1. APOL4 - Individual genes

The following genes were found to show high rankings along with APOL4 - USH1 protein network component harmonin (USH1C), ST6 beta-galactoside alpha-2,6-sialyltransferase 1 (ST6GAL1), oxysterol binding protein like 6 (OSBPL6), secretagogin, EF-hand calcium binding protein (SCGN), parathyroid hormone like hormone (PTH1LH), solute carrier family 7 member 8 (SLC7A8), protein kinase C and casein kinase substrate in neurons 2 (PACSIN2), WAP four-disulfide core domain 2 (WFDC2), mesothelin (MSLN), junctophilin 1 (JPH1), neurocalcin delta (NCALD), annexin A13 (ANXA13), tight junction protein 3 (TJP3), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), RUN domain containing 3B (RUNDC3B), nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT), cordon-bleu WH2 repeat protein (COBL), protein arginine methyltransferase 8 (PRMT8), sodium channel epithelial 1 subunit alpha (SCNN1A), RNA binding motif protein 24 (RBM24), leucine rich repeat containing 31 (LRRC31), peroxisomal biogenesis factor 5 like (PEX5L), interleukin 1 receptor like 1 (IL1RL1), melanophilin (MLPH), 24-dehydrocholesterol reductase (DHCR24), interferon regulatory factor 6 (IRF6), phospholipid phosphatase related 4 (PLPPR4), periplakin (PPL), cyclin and CBS domain divalent metal cation transport mediator 1 (CNNM1), SRY-box transcription factor 9 (SOX9), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 2 (PCSK2), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 2 (HSPA2), G protein subunit alpha z

(GNAZ), filamin C (FLNC), kallikrein related peptidase 10 (KLK10), kallikrein related peptidase 8 (KLK8), EPS8 signaling adaptor L1 (EPS8L1), microtubule associated scaffold protein 2 (MTUS2), brain expressed X-linked 2 (BEX2), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), ETS homologous factor (EHF), KLF transcription factor 4 (KLF4), KIAA0319, FXYD domain containing ion transport regulator 6 (FXYD6), RasGEF domain family member 1B (RASGEF1B), cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), shisa like 1 (SHISAL1 / KIAA1644), MAM domain containing glycosylphosphatidylinositol anchor 2 (MDGA2), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), PR/SET domain 16 (PRDM16), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), maelstrom spermatogenic transposon silencer (MAEL), immunoglobulin like domain containing receptor 2 (ILDR2), sushi domain containing 4 (SUSD4), polypeptide N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase 13 (GALNT13), atypical chemokine receptor 3 (ACKR3), glutamate decarboxylase like 1 (GADL1), gamma-aminobutyric acid type A receptor subunit beta2 (GABRB2), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), solute carrier family 26 member 7 (SLC26A7), cadherin 8 (CDH8), family with sequence similarity 124 member A (FAM124A), coiled-coil domain containing 3 (CCDC3), F-box protein 32 (FBXO32), grainyhead like transcription factor 3 (GRHL3), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 6B2 (COX6B2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), AKNA domain containing 1 (AKNAD1), sphingosine-1-phosphate phosphatase 2 (SGPP2), carboxypeptidase A3 (CPA3), neuropeptide Y receptor Y1 (NPY1R), hyperpolarization activated cyclic nucleotide gated potassium channel 1 (HCN1), adenylate cyclase 1 (ADCY1), defensin beta 1 (DEFB1), lysine demethylase 1B (KDM1B), solute carrier family 16 member 9 (SLC16A9), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1), serpin family B member 8 (SERPINB8), pleckstrin homology domain containing A7 (PLEKHA7), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase 1 (GPD1), phospholipase A and acyltransferase 5 (PLAAT5 / HRASLS5), bradykinin receptor B2 (BDKRB2), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein (PHYHIP), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), kallikrein related peptidase 7 (KLK7), RAB3B, member RAS oncogene family (RAB3B), mucin 3A, cell surface associated (MUC3A), DLG associated protein 1 (DLGAP1), CDC42 binding protein kinase gamma (CDC42BPG), potassium two pore domain channel subfamily K member 3 (KCNK3), lysophosphatidic acid receptor 3 (LPAR3), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), angiotensin like 7 (ANGPTL7), tryptase alpha/beta 1 (TPSAB1), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), syntrophin gamma 2 (SNTG2), myosin ID (MYO1D), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 2 (KCNA2), reprimin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM), endoplasmic reticulum to nucleus signaling 1 (ERN1), cadherin 4 (CDH4), transmembrane protein 30B (TMEM30B), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), family with sequence similarity 162 member B (FAM162B), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member A3 (ALDH1A3), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), brain expressed X-linked 5 (BEX5), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), potassium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KCNIP4), piccolo presynaptic cytomatrix pro-

tein (PCLO), insulin induced gene 1 (INSIG1), forkhead box I2 (FOXI2), keratin 16 (KRT16), pyroglutamylated RFamide peptide receptor (QRFPR), tryptase beta 2 (TPSB2), aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10 (AKR1B10), DDB1 and CUL4 associated factor 12 like 2 (DCAF12L2), collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1), family with sequence similarity 120A2, pseudogene (FAM120A2P / C9orf129) and SEC14 like lipid binding 6 (SEC14L6).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to tabulate 2nd order combinations of APOL4 with these genes, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1].

Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS APOL4									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T APOL4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
USH1C - APOL4	22	242	206	264	ST6GAL1 - APOL4	245	263	2	207
OSBPL6 - APOL4	222	156	6	142	SCGN - APOL4	133	247	136	290
PTHLH - APOL4	6	201	133	212	SLC7A8 - APOL4	275	280	22	156
PACSIN2 - APOL4	296	233	8	147	WFDC2 - APOL4	237	287	186	291
MSLN - APOL4	265	120	205	235	NCALD - APOL4	251	134	110	175
JPH1 - APOL4	214	177	119	187	ANXA13 - APOL4	261	121	296	285
TJP3 - APOL4	191	54	135	277	GRIK5 - APOL4	156	44	139	295
RUNDC3B - APOL4	132	303	200	180	NAMPT - APOL4	59	213	301	151
COBL - APOL4	218	227	214	258	PRMT8 - APOL4	197	183	30	276
SCNN1A - APOL4	24	274	271	162	RBM24 - APOL4	136	167	152	304
LRRC31 - APOL4	224	108	180	201	PEX5L - APOL4	225	118	246	206
IL1RL1 - APOL4	279	149	79	209	MLPH - APOL4	207	264	66	271
DHCR24 - APOL4	244	240	178	186	IRF6 - APOL4	158	112	138	173
PLPPR4 - APOL4	303	229	29	242	PPL - APOL4	223	88	131	248
CNNM1 - APOL4	184	209	157	171	SOX9 - APOL4	299	185	32	247
PCSK2 - APOL4	159	150	44	229	HSPA2 - APOL4	199	189	258	39
GNAZ - APOL4	216	266	172	157	FLNC - APOL4	186	279	170	98
KLK10 - APOL4	287	235	122	214	KLK8 - APOL4	292	142	83	238
EPS8L1 - APOL4	150	192	167	34	MTUS2 - APOL4	217	151	166	225
BEX2 - APOL4	174	294	115	202	LARGE1 - APOL4	46	285	244	255
EHF - APOL4	119	178	197	283	KLF4 - APOL4	117	305	227	146
KIAA0319 - APOL4	137	296	224	72	FXYP6 - APOL4	236	212	108	221
RASGEF1B - APOL4	8	197	267	136	CDKL2 - APOL4	205	275	193	61
KIAA1644 - APOL4	250	179	174	140	MDGA2 - APOL4	210	115	220	183
RNF157 - APOL4	129	230	275	190	SLC47A1 - APOL4	178	2	187	270
PRDM16 - APOL4	163	180	234	29	SLC44A3 - APOL4	175	236	169	45
MAEL - APOL4	272	298	39	246	ILDR2 - APOL4	295	195	28	234
SUSD4 - APOL4	189	202	111	257	GALNT13 - APOL4	304	277	93	192
ACKR3 - APOL4	171	301	82	149	GADL1 - APOL4	293	286	43	251
GABRB2 - APOL4	220	161	85	226	PRSS35 - APOL4	49	259	305	160
SLC26A7 - APOL4	276	141	59	218	CDH8 - APOL4	111	271	165	196
FAM124A - APOL4	148	159	265	297	CCDC3 - APOL4	231	148	142	188

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between APOL4 VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - ● Individual members w.r.t APOL4 with APOL4 – > .

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS APOL4									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T APOL4									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
FBXO32 - APOL4	164	145	182	249	GRHL3 - APOL4	260	186	233	170
ACE - APOL4	130	199	201	293	COX6B2 - APOL4	181	165	33	259
CHRN2 - APOL4	198	260	146	41	CYP3A4 - APOL4	147	78	295	292
AKNAD1 - APOL4	239	228	164	199	SGPP2 - APOL4	282	300	132	268
CPA3 - APOL4	228	139	112	191	NPY1R - APOL4	283	136	120	240
HCN1 - APOL4	280	143	114	215	ADCY1 - APOL4	19	211	211	194
DEFB1 - APOL4	273	216	104	245	KDM1B - APOL4	179	283	270	300
SLC16A9 - APOL4	201	215	160	220	CACNB2 - APOL4	177	293	263	112
SPINT1 - APOL4	149	153	294	177	SERPINB8 - APOL4	39	220	202	131
PLEKHA7 - APOL4	152	38	251	141	ANPEP - APOL4	180	166	171	127
GPD1 - APOL4	202	288	153	176	HRASLS5 - APOL4	290	258	101	274
BDKRB2 - APOL4	274	132	150	227	PHYHIP - APOL4	234	289	100	272
NSG1 - APOL4	263	292	154	298	KLK7 - APOL4	305	187	76	233
RAB3B - APOL4	185	297	102	296	MUC3A - APOL4	247	218	25	232
DLGAP1 - APOL4	240	302	129	174	CDC42BPG - APOL4	151	176	226	35
KCNK3 - APOL4	252	256	64	205	LPAR3 - APOL4	269	160	67	185
CFAP46 - APOL4	106	254	213	139	ANGPTL7 - APOL4	144	130	181	307
TPSAB1 - APOL4	248	158	162	198	SPTLC3 - APOL4	20	200	290	158
CSDC2 - APOL4	173	137	95	273	RCAN2 - APOL4	38	241	264	145
SNTG2 - APOL4	300	146	151	237	MYO1D - APOL4	246	249	70	282
KCNA2 - APOL4	139	250	185	306	RPRM - APOL4	284	217	84	252
ERN1 - APOL4	9	214	229	152	CDH4 - APOL4	302	147	46	231
TMEM30B - APOL4	142	261	247	37	RIPK4 - APOL4	206	126	141	197
FAM162B - APOL4	155	272	273	269	ALDH1A3 - APOL4	166	155	261	281
CCSER1 - APOL4	204	170	184	48	BEX5 - APOL4	153	83	159	193
SDR42E1 - APOL4	294	225	96	256	KCNIP4 - APOL4	306	255	54	262
PCLO - APOL4	242	70	134	213	INSIG1 - APOL4	13	191	278	154
FOXI2 - APOL4	227	232	41	254	KRT16 - APOL4	264	299	74	253
QRFR - APOL4	289	226	34	265	TPSB2 - APOL4	270	190	130	159
AKR1B10 - APOL4	253	152	72	241	DCAF12L2 - APOL4	215	172	52	203
COL15A1 - APOL4	123	278	176	150	C9orf129 - APOL4	138	174	189	83
SEC14L6 - APOL4	301	87	149	278	- APOL4				

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between APOL4 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic APOL4 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of APOL4-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t APOL4

USH1C / ST6GAL1 / OSBPL6 / SCGN / PTHLH ...	
SLC7A8 / PACSIN2 / WFDC2 / MSLN / NCALD ...	
JPH1 / ANXA13 / TJP3 / GRIK5 / RUNDC3B ...	
NAMPT / COBL / PRMT8 / SCNN1A / RBM24 ...	
LRRC31 / PEX5L / IL1RL1 / MLPH / DHCR24 ...	
IRF6 / PLPPR4 / PPL / CNNM1 / SOX9 / PCSK2 ...	
HSPA2 / GNAZ / FLNC / KLK10 / KLK8 / EPS8L1 ...	
MTUS2 / BEX2 / LARGE1 / EHF / KLF4 / KIAA0319 ...	
FXYD6 / RASGEF1B / CDKL2 / KIAA1644 / MDGA2 ...	
RNF157 / SLC47A1 / PRDM16 / SLC44A3 / MAEL ...	
ILDR2 / SUSL4 / GALNT13 / ACKR3 / GADL1 ...	
GABRB2 / PRSS35 / SLC26A7 / CDH8 / FAM124A ...	
CCDC3 / FBXO32 / GRHL3 / ACE / COX6B2 / CHRNB2 ...	
CYP3A4 / AKNAD1 / SGPP2 / CPA3 / NPY1R / HCN1 ...	
ADCY1 / DEFB1 / KDM1B / SLC16A9 / CACNB2 / ...	
SPINT1 / SERPINB8 / PLEKHA7 / ANPEP / GPD1 ...	
HRASLS5 / BDKRB2 / PHYHIP / NSG1 / KLK7 / ...	
RAB3B / MUC3A / DLGAP1 / CDC42BPG / KCNK3 ...	
LPAR3 / CFAP46 / ANGPTL7 / TPSAB1 / SPTLC3 ...	
CSDC2 / RCAN2 / SNTG2 / MYO1D / KCNA2 / RPRM ...	
ERN1 / CDH4 / TMEM30B / RIPK4 / FAM162B ...	
ALDH1A3 / CCSER1 / BEX5 / SDR42E1 / KCNIP4 ...	
PCLO / INSIG1 / FOXI2 / KRT16 / QRFPR ...	
TPSB2 / AKR1B10 / DCAF12L2 / COL15A1 ...	
C9orf129 / SEC14L6	APOL4

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between APOL4 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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